

Hot-Carrier-Induced Electron Trapping in the Drift Region of N-Type LDMOS Devices at Deep-Cryogenic Temperatures

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Abstract—The growing demand for quantum computing applications requires reliable semiconductor devices operating at deep-cryogenic temperatures. While CMOS reliability at cryogenic temperatures has been extensively studied, high-voltage laterally-diffused metal-oxide semiconductor (LDMOS) devices required for quantum applications such as ion shuttling remain largely unexplored. This paper investigates the reliability of n-type LDMOS devices from room temperature down to the deep-cryogenic regime, focusing on hot-carrier degradation. At temperatures below 40 K, LDMOS devices exhibit a diode-like behavior in their output characteristics due to the freeze-out of charge carriers in the drift region. We demonstrate that electron trapping in shallow traps at the Si-SiO₂ interface of the drift region significantly affects this behavior. We model this effect using an equivalent circuit consisting of a depletion MOSFET with floating gate for the drift region. This model is validated using a modified LDMOS device with an additional poly gate, allowing direct measurement of its threshold voltage shifts.

Index Terms—cryogenic, cryo-CMOS, electron trapping, LDMOS, freeze-out, hot-carrier stress, reliability

I. INTRODUCTION

CRYO-CMOS is receiving increased focus as more applications and the interest in devices working down to deep-cryogenic temperatures is rising. One of the main driving fields is quantum computing as it requires deep-cryogenic temperatures for operation. The race for higher qubit counts drives the need to integrate supplementary electronics close to the qubits. This exposes conventional silicon-based devices to a new, much lower operating regime. [1]

While the reliability of low-voltage CMOS down to the deep-cryogenic regime has already been investigated in [2]–[4],

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some applications require the use of high-voltage devices. Scaling trapped-ion qubits requires shuttling operations moving ions by means of electric fields up to a few tens of volts [5]. This is beyond the capabilities of CMOS devices and requires the use of high voltage laterally-diffused metal-oxide semiconductor (LDMOS) devices for some parts of the control logic.

Operating LDMOS devices in the deep-cryogenic regime poses a challenge to both the device model and control of the characteristics as well as the reliability. The freeze-out of the charge carriers alters the behavior of the device and is discussed in Sec. II-A and II-B. The reliability of LDMOS devices due to hot-carriers is expected to be worse at cryogenic temperatures due to the increase in mean free path and therefore higher energy of the charge carriers. However, this topic has not yet been covered in the literature. In this paper, we will investigate the reliability of LDMOS devices under hot-carrier stress covering a temperature range from room temperature down to the deep-cryogenic regime.

II. BACKGROUND

A. Deep-cryogenic temperatures and freeze-out

At deep-cryogenic temperatures, the characteristics of silicon deviate significantly from those at room temperature. In the conventional operating regime above 200 K, the number of free charge carriers can directly be influenced by the number of dopant atoms as almost all of them are ionized. This direct relation between doping concentration and characteristics of the semiconductor material is more complex at lower temperatures, as the thermal energy of the charge carriers might not be sufficient to overcome the difference between the impurity energy level and the band edge. Increasing the doping concentration does not necessarily lead to a corresponding increase in charge carriers that contribute to the current transport.

For phosphorus-doped n-type silicon, the number of ionized charge carriers is plotted in Fig. 1 for temperatures below 150 K and doping concentrations ranging from $1 \times 10^{12} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ to $1 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$. The data in the figure was obtained in two steps. First, the charge neutrality equation is solved for the Fermi level E_F following the steps described by Sze in [6]. For the next step, we use the results from Beckers et al. [7]. They describe that assuming incomplete ionization, the simplified Boltzmann statistics for the calculation of E_F

Fig. 1. Number of ionized donors N_D^+ for doping concentrations from $N_D = 1 \times 10^{12} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ to $1 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ and temperatures below 150 K.

Fig. 2. Simplified n-type LDMOS device with shallow trench isolation (STI). Parts of the drift region not covered by the gate (marked with x) suffer from freeze-out.

can be used. At deep-cryogenic temperatures towards 0 K, the Fermi level approaches a level midway between the conduction band edge and the dopant energy level $(E_C - E_D)/2$. This behavior is independent of the doping level and ensures that the separation between the Fermi level and conduction band edge is sufficiently large at all temperatures to allow the use of the Boltzmann statistics ($E_C - E_F > 3k_B T$). With the result for E_F and material parameters, the number of ionized donors is calculated for different doping concentrations and temperatures $T \leq 150 \text{ K}$.

For high doping concentrations, incomplete ionization influences the characteristics even at 150 K in Fig. 1. With decreasing doping concentration, the threshold temperature for the transition between complete and incomplete ionization decreases to around 40 K for $N_D = 1 \times 10^{12} \text{ cm}^{-3}$. At temperatures below that threshold, N_D^+ decreases exponentially causing a freeze-out of the charge carriers and prohibiting them from taking part in the current transport.

B. LDMOS characteristics at cryogenic temperatures

The simplified geometry of the n-type LDMOS device under investigation is shown in Fig. 2. The body and source contacts are shorted and the drift region features a shallow trench isolation (STI). The gate electrode covers the channel and parts of the drift region. In Fig. 2, the part of the drift region that is not covered by the gate is marked with x. These two regions need to be treated separately, as the electric field from the gate electrode has significant impact and is able to change the previously explained characteristics at cryogenic temperatures. The field can change the band structure so that flat-band conditions no longer exist. The band bending lowers the barrier of the impurity well allowing charge carriers to

Fig. 3. Output characteristics for low V_{DS} values up to 0.5 V of an n-type LDMOS device at cryogenic temperatures. Starting at 60 K, the diode-like behavior starts to change the device characteristics for low V_{DS} values and its influence increases towards lower temperatures.

either pass over the barrier or to tunnel through a now thinner potential wall. This field-assisted ionization allows for normal operation of CMOS devices as long as the gate covers the entire channel region between the source and drain contact. [8] This effect has an influence on the characteristics of the LDMOS device as well, but only those parts covered by the gate electrode. In the other parts (marked with x), the freeze-out effects cannot be compensated and affect the device characteristics. The impact on the output characteristics is shown in Fig. 3. The linear region at low V_{DS} values changes at temperatures of 60 K and below from a linear to a diode-like behavior. The electric field required to compensate for the thermal freeze-out is created by a potential difference within the drift region.

This behavior was already described by Kaushal and Mohapatra in [9] and [10] who modeled the characteristics of n-type LDMOS devices down to 77 K where they already observed first signs of this effect. They separated the individual elements of on-state resistance into their main two elements, the channel and drift region. The value of the first one decreased with temperature down to the lowest temperature while the latter decreased only down to 140 K. At lower temperatures, the resistance of the drift region increases again due to freeze-out. The threshold temperature of 140 K can also be seen in Fig. 1 for a doping concentration of around $1 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ that is typical for the drift region. The exponential decrease of the ionized donors starts at that temperature.

The evaluation of the LDMOS characteristics of Zahra et al. [11] extends this discussion down to the deep-cryogenic regime. They report an exponential increase of the on-state resistance and diode-like behavior with an increase in threshold voltage towards lower temperatures, similar to our device shown in Fig. 3. In a follow-up, they add an additional poly gate on top of the drift region to compensate for most of the freeze-out effects [12]. This concept will be applied later in Sec. IV where we use a similar device for our reliability investigations as it allows for more control and also an additional way to probe the characteristics of the drift region.

C. Hot-carrier lifetime evaluation

To evaluate the lifetime of LDMOS devices, we first use the classical methods for hot-carrier stress (HCS). For the measurement itself, the devices are stressed using a stress-measure-stress routine. The HCS test is an on-state stress at maximum drain voltage with an experimentally derived gate voltage corresponding to the maximum degradation. We stress the device in multiple intervals with increasing duration to allow for intermediate measurements of the device parameters. This routine allows us to determine the degradation in relation to the initial characteristics measured before the first stress interval.

The criterion we use in this paper is a degradation of the linear on-state resistance by 10%. The stress time required to reach this target defines the lifetime of the device. In Fig. 4, the lifetime of an n-type LDMOS device stressed at temperatures from 300 K down to 77 K is plotted. At higher temperatures above 100 K, we can fit the data with the classical Arrhenius function. The data points for 100 K and even 77 K follow this trend as well, but the calculated lifetime for those two has to be considered with caution as it is much shorter than the first stress interval. This means that the drift criterion was already exceeded at the first readout of the stress-measure-stress routine. The lifetime is therefore an extrapolation of the data to lower stress times. The reason for this behavior is that the degradation of the on-state resistance after the first stress interval (1 s HCS) is already close to 100% leading to an arbitrarily low lifetime. Below 77 K, there is an additional limiting factor in evaluating the measurement data: To prevent unrealistically low values, we set a lower bound for the extrapolated lifetime of 1×10^{-10} s and exclude all data points below this threshold.

1) *Adapted stress method for cryogenic temperatures*: To avoid the high degradation within the first stress interval that prevents us from evaluating the lifetime at 60 K and below, we use a different method. Instead of the conventional HCS condition $V_{DS} = V_{DS,max}$, we use short $I_{D,sat}$ measurements (see Fig. 5) with increasing drain voltage to stress one device. After each step, the linear DC parameters are measured to evaluate the degradation caused by the previous $I_{D,sat}$ pulse. This approach cannot be compared to the method discussed above in Sec. II-C and does not allow for a lifetime evaluation, but it enables us to describe the effect that causes the high instantaneous degradation.

III. RESULTS

A. Output characteristics

To evaluate the degradation and also to explain the characteristics observed for the classical HCS routine, we focus on the output characteristics of the device. In Fig. 6, the output characteristics at 3 K before the initial and after selected $I_{D,sat}$ stress pulses are shown. To avoid any additional stress and to focus on the linear region of the device, the output characteristics are only measured up to a drain voltage of $V_{DS} = 0.5$ V. Stress pulses with drain voltages lower than $V_{DS} = 13$ V do not lead to a change in the characteristics. Starting from 13 V, we observe a small change that increases with increasing stress

Fig. 4. Lifetime of an n-type LDMOS device at temperatures from 300 K down to 77 K. Data from lower temperatures is excluded due to unrealistically short lifetimes below 1×10^{-10} s. The drift criterion for the lifetime is a degradation of $\Delta I_{D,lin}$ by 10% measured at $V_{DS} = 0.1$ V.

Fig. 5. The devices are stressed by multiple short $I_{D,sat}$ measurement points with increasing drain voltage. The readout of the linear device parameters is done at the beginning and after each $I_{D,sat}$ stress.

voltage. Compared to the initial measurement, the diode-like characteristics become more pronounced. Starting with a stress pulse with an amplitude of $V_{DS} = 17$ V, the device does not conduct any current for V_{DS} just above 0 V and requires a certain threshold voltage $V_{DS,th}$ to turn on. With increasing stress voltage, this offset increases to more than 300 mV for $V_{DS,stress} = 40$ V.

This behavior explains the observed instantaneous degradation using the HCS evaluation method explained in Sec. II-C. The on-state resistance is measured at a drain voltage of $V_{DS,lin} = 0.1$ V. The drain threshold voltage caused by pulses with $V_{DS,stress} \geq 20$ V is larger than the drain voltage used to measure the on-state resistance causing a degradation of close to 100%. One solution would be to change the measurement conditions used for the on-state resistance, but even at $V_{DS} = 0.5$ V, we see significant influence of the drain threshold voltage after $V_{DS,stress} = 40$ V. By choosing an even higher drain voltage for the on-state resistance, we could reduce the calculated degradation, but this decision would be arbitrary. This HCS-induced offset is the reason for introducing the adapted stress method shown in Fig. 5 as it allows us to investigate this behavior.

After the measurement, the sample is heated up to room temperature by moving it out of the cryo stage. After a few hours, the sample is put back into the cryo stage and cooled down to 3 K. The same $I_{D,sat}$ stress routine with intermediate parameter readout is repeated on the same device. The results of the second run are plotted in Fig. 6 with dashed lines. We see that the temperature cycle leads to a partial recovery of

Fig. 6. Output characteristics for low V_{DS} values up to 0.5 V measured on one device after multiple $I_{D,sat}$ stress pulses with increasing drain voltage and at a temperature of 3 K. The readouts are performed at positions marked with "lin. param." in Fig. 5. The dashed curves were measured by repeating the routine on the same device after a temperature cycle up to room temperature and back down to 3 K.

the device characteristics. Starting with a stress pulse with $V_{DS, stress} = 20$ V, the characteristics of the second run are similar to those of the first run.

B. Temperature characteristics

For the evaluation of the temperature characteristics of the drain threshold voltage, we use $V_{DS, th} = V_{DS}(I_D=1 \text{ nA})$ as a criterion to define the threshold voltage. It is one order of magnitude above the measurement noise and the drain current characteristics are exponential for all curves in Fig. 6. The measurement is performed by forcing a current of 1 nA at the drain node of every device. To get the temperature characteristics, we measure the corresponding threshold voltage $V_{DS, th}$ during the cool-down of the cryostat. Apart from the reference device, which is not stressed and used to obtain the characteristics without stress, all of them are stressed with a short $V_{DS, stress} = 40$ V pulse, after which the temperature characteristics of the offset voltage $V_{DS, th}$ are measured. One device is stressed at room temperature, one at 80 K and the last one at 3 K. For the two devices stressed at cryogenic temperatures, we repeat the measurement of the temperature-dependent offset characteristics after heating the devices to room temperature, without applying any additional stress.

The temperature-dependent offset voltages under all three stress conditions and the reference device are plotted in Fig. 7. For the stressed devices, the characteristics start to deviate around 30 K from the reference. The offsets of the two samples stressed at cryogenic temperatures start at slightly different temperatures, but at around 20 K, they converge and can be considered identical for temperatures close to the absolute minimum. The reference sample in comparison only shows an increase in offset around 10 K to 15 K and its absolute value towards 0 K is also much lower. This is in line with the characteristics in Fig. 6 with the reference representing the 0 V curve and the devices stressed at 3 K representing the 40 V curve. Similar to the output characteristics, the same measurement is repeated after a cycle to room temperature and then back to 3 K. We see again a partial recovery of the device degradation. The characteristics of the two devices are

Fig. 7. Offset threshold voltage $V_{DS, th}$ measured by forcing a drain current of $I_D = 1$ nA at the drain terminal of the LDMOS device. The characteristics were measured during a cool-down process of the sample. For the stressed devices, the applied stress is one single $I_{D, sat}$ pulse with $V_{DS, stress} = 40$ V.

now much closer to the ones of the reference device, but the offset is still higher.

The device stressed at room temperature shows similar characteristics to the ones stressed at cryogenic temperatures before the temperature cycle, but its offset value towards 0 K is significantly lower. Compared to the same devices after the temperature cycle however, the offset is much higher. Despite being at room temperature for a few minutes after the stress, the offset is very pronounced. This behavior indicates trapping of charge carriers at shallow traps at the Si-SiO₂ interface as discussed in the next section.

C. Characteristics of traps

In this section, we discuss the origin of the offset characteristics that are observed after applying high $V_{DS, stress}$ to the device. We argue that electrons in shallow traps at the Si-SiO₂ interface are responsible for this behavior. At deep-cryogenic temperatures, charges trapped in the oxide can have significant impact on the characteristics of the drift region. Due to freeze-out, small amounts of charge are sufficient to alter the electrostatics within the drift region. Several aspects of our experimental observations support this conclusion.

1) *Characteristics of shallow traps at cryogenic temperatures:* At cryogenic temperatures, the characteristics of the traps change significantly. While the trapping of electrons is significantly enhanced, the creation of new traps is inhibited. [13]

The temperature-dependent offset characteristics in Fig. 7 of devices stressed at 80 K and 3 K are very similar for most temperatures. Shallow traps are located at or very close to the Si-SiO₂ interface. The small difference in distance and energy leads to similar trapping characteristics within this temperature range [14].

2) *Recovery after temperature cycle to RT:* In the output characteristics in Fig. 6 and temperature dependence of the offset in Fig. 7, we see a recovery of the device after a cycle to room temperature. This is in line with the behavior of shallow traps described in the literature. Itsumi investigated the trapping characteristics in a MOS capacitor and saw a re-emission rate of 70% to 80% of electrons trapped at 77 K

Fig. 8. Equivalent circuit model for the LDMOS device consisting of an enhancement MOSFET for the channel and a depletion MOSFET for the drift region. The trapped charge in the oxide of the drift region is modeled with the gate charge of the depletion device.

after the sample was warmed up to 296 K. This is also an indicator of the energy level of the traps, as they need to be on the order of $k_B T$ at room temperature (≈ 25 meV) to be influenced by the temperature cycle. [15]

We do not see a full recovery of the characteristics for two possible reasons. While electrons mainly populate the shallow traps at cryogenic temperatures, they can also be trapped at lower energy levels. A second possibility is that electrons trapped in shallow traps undergo a transition to a lower level out of reach for detrapping at room temperature. [16]

Due to the enhanced occupation but inhibited creation of traps at cryogenic temperatures [13], the characteristics do not change if the device is stressed a second time. Starting at a stress pulse amplitude of 20 V, the difference in the output characteristics in Fig. 6 before and after the temperature cycle is negligible.

3) *LDMOS device stressed at room temperature*: The shallow traps that dominate the behavior at cryogenic temperatures cannot be populated at room temperature as the emission time is very short. The reason for this is the shallow energy level in combination with the much higher thermal energy at room temperature that allows the charge carriers to escape their traps. This means that these shallow traps cannot be the reason for the higher offset characteristics at cryogenic temperatures. At higher temperatures, the electrons are trapped at deeper energy levels that do not allow re-emission at room temperature. Cooling the sample down decreases the chance of emission even further. At deep-cryogenic temperatures, those trapped charges influence the device characteristics. [16]

D. Device model

To describe the trapping of electrons in the SiO_2 above the drift region, we introduce a modified equivalent circuit model in Fig. 8. The channel region is modeled with a conventional enhancement MOSFET with a gate that can be controlled from the outside. To describe the behavior of the drift region at cryogenic temperatures, we use a depletion n-type MOSFET. The trapped charge influences the characteristics similarly to a poly gate, which is why the gate contact is not connected and is floating.

IV. LDMOS DEVICE WITH ADDITIONAL POLY GATE

To verify the device model proposed in the previous section, we use a modified LDMOS device structure shown in Fig. 9. The device is very similar to the one in Fig. 2, which we used to evaluate the offset characteristics in Sec. III. The difference

Fig. 9. LDMOS device similar to Fig. 2, but with additional poly gate above the drift region.

Fig. 10. Output characteristics of the n-type LDMOS device with additional poly gate before (0 V) and after $I_{D,\text{sat}}$ stress at drain voltages of $V_{DS} = 30$ V, 35 V and 40 V. The lines were measured with $V_{\text{poly gate}} = 0$ V (solid), 1 V (dashed) and 3 V (dotted) applied to the poly gate of the device. The device was measured at a temperature of 3 K.

is that there is now an additional poly gate on top of the drift region. The other minor change is a small reduction of the gate size that was necessary to accommodate the poly gate. This allows us to control the previously floating gate of the depletion MOSFET to get more insight into the shift of its threshold voltage.

In Fig. 10, the measurement from Fig. 6 featuring the output characteristics measured after short $V_{DS,\text{stress}}$ pulses is repeated. The curves for the three different values of $V_{\text{poly gate}}$ were measured on the same device without any additional stress in between and starting with the lowest value of 0 V. Focusing on the characteristics with $V_{\text{poly gate}} = 0$ V, we see similar characteristics as before. The absolute values for the offset are different due to differences in the device geometry, but the trend is the same. Increasing the potential of the poly gate reduces the offset significantly, but it cannot compensate for the whole offset. The trend of increasing offset with increasing stress voltage is less pronounced, but still observable.

A. Transfer characteristics of drift region

The additional poly gate allows us to probe the threshold voltage shift of the depletion MOSFET used to model the behavior of the drift region. To do this, we measure conventional transfer characteristics, but instead of sweeping the gate voltage, we vary the potential of the poly gate. To minimize the impact of the channel region and focus on only the changes caused by the drift region, we apply a voltage of $V_{GS} = 3.75$ V $\gg V_{th}$ to the gate of the device.

In Fig. 11, the transfer characteristics of the drift region

Fig. 11. Drain current measured for a voltage sweep of the poly gate for $V_{GS} = 3.75$ V and $V_{DS} = 0.2$ V. The transfer characteristics of the drift region were measured on the same device after $I_{D,sat}$ stress with increasing drain voltage and at a temperature of 3 K.

measured after short $I_{D,sat}$ pulses with increasing drain voltage are plotted. Similar to the output characteristics, we see a change at higher drain voltages of $V_{DS, stress} = 20$ V or higher. With increasing stress, we see a shift of the transfer characteristics towards higher levels with a threshold voltage of just above 0 V before stress to more than 3 V at maximum stress $V_{DS, stress} = 40$ V. These characteristics are similar to those of a (depletion) MOSFET device that experiences a shift of its threshold voltage due to degradation and/or charge trapping at the gate oxide.

B. Estimate for number of trapped electrons

With the transfer characteristics of the depletion MOSFET in Fig. 11, we can make an estimation about the density of the trapped electrons that cause the shift in threshold voltage. As we discussed in Sec. III-C, the trapped electrons are stationary at deep-cryogenic temperatures and are not re-emitted from their traps unless we heat up the sample. Using this assumption, we can estimate the number of trapped electrons N_{it} based on the threshold voltage shift ΔV_{th} : [17]

$$N_{it} = \frac{\Delta V_{th} \cdot C_{OX}}{q} \quad (1)$$

The only additional device parameter we need is the thickness of the oxide between the poly gate and drift region which is 400 nm for our device.

The definition of the threshold voltage shift is a bit more difficult. One option is to choose the value of $I_D = 1$ nA we also used in previous sections of this paper. The advantage is that we can easily determine the corresponding voltage shift as all characteristics surpass that threshold and have similar characteristics that should minimize the error. The downside of this approach is that the commonly used current criterion for the threshold voltage also found in data sheets is around 1×10^{-6} A for our device. Due to the different characteristics of the curves, the difference in threshold voltage would be higher. In addition, the characteristics of the highest two stress voltages do not reach that value for the selected sweep range of V_{poly} .

For the following estimations whose results are shown in

Table I, we use two criteria and use them as upper and lower bound. The lower threshold is around 1×10^{-10} A as this is slightly below the change in gradient of the characteristics for $V_{DS, stress} = 40$ V. The second threshold we use is 1×10^{-7} A as it is again below a change in gradient for all but the highest two stress voltages and much closer to the typical values used to determine V_{th} .

TABLE I

ESTIMATE FOR NUMBER OF TRAPPED ELECTRONS AFTER SELECTED STRESS PULSES. THE THRESHOLD VOLTAGE USED FOR THE CALCULATIONS IS OBTAINED FROM DATA SHOWN IN FIG. 11.

	27.5 V	30 V	32.5 V	35 V	37.5 V	40 V
$N_{it 10^{-10} A} / (10^{11} \text{ cm}^{-2})$	0.22	0.35	0.66	1.05	1.59	1.62
$N_{it 10^{-7} A} / (10^{11} \text{ cm}^{-2})$	0.19	0.35	0.70	1.32	(2.16)	-

As we see in Table I, the criterion for the threshold voltage has only minor influence as long as the gradient of the transfer characteristics do not change between the individual curves. Only for the highest two stress voltages, we cannot use the 1×10^{-7} A criterion. The result for the $V_{DS, stress} = 37.5$ V is therefore only in brackets as its value is unrealistically high. Comparing the results to the literature, we see a relatively good match. The trend of saturating trap density with increasing drain voltage (equivalent to increasing electric fields) matches the qualitative results from DiMaria [13]. Comparing the absolute numbers is more difficult for two reasons. As our device is in the on-state during stress, we cannot measure or separate the charge that is injected into the interface. Secondly, the potential within the drift region is not constant leading to an inhomogeneous electric field in the oxide. For this reason, we only do a rough check to see if our numbers in Table I are plausible. They are in the order of magnitude of 10^{10} cm^{-2} to 10^{11} cm^{-2} which is also comparable to data found in literature [18], [19] and therefore passes this plausibility check.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have investigated the reliability of LDMOS devices covering both the classical and the cryogenic regime. At temperatures $T \geq 100$ K, we can use the classical hot-carrier stress routines and evaluation methods. At cryogenic temperatures and especially at temperatures below 40 K, this approach is no longer valid as the freeze-out of the charge carriers, especially in the drift region, alters the device characteristics. Diode-like behavior in the output characteristics for low V_{DS} values is caused by the exponential increase in resistance and is very sensitive to electrons trapped in shallow traps at the Si-SiO₂ interface. These trapped electrons introduce an additional offset voltage of up to several hundred millivolts. Due to their shallow energy level, most of the electrons can be detrapped by heating the sample to room temperature, confirming the trapping mechanism. This behavior of the drift region can be modeled with a depletion MOSFET featuring a floating gate representing the trapped electrons.

This device model was verified using a modified LDMOS device that features an additional poly gate over the drift region. Measuring the transfer characteristics of that depletion

MOSFET before and after different stress conditions allows us to quantify the shift in threshold voltage caused by the trapped electrons.

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